

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND SURFACE CHARACTERIZATION OF PECTIN EXTRACTED FROM ORANGE PEEL AND REINFORCED IN PLA COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: This study explores the development of polylactic acid (PLA) composites reinforced with varying percentages of pectin extracted from orange peel. The aim is to create sustainable alternatives to polyethylene (PE) for various applications, considering mechanical properties, hydrophilicity, and biodegradability. Pectin was extracted using citric acid, and PLA-pectin composites were prepared with pectin content ranging from 0% to 3%. Mechanical testing, hardness evaluation, thermal conductivity measurements, and water contact angle assessments were conducted according to ASTM standards. The results indicated that incorporating pectin enhances tensile strength (ranging from 3.86 N/mm² to 4.95 N/mm²) and elongation at break (9.99% to 19.15%) while improving hydrophilicity. These properties suggest that PLA-pectin composites can effectively replace PE in rigid and flexible packaging, single-use items, and agricultural applications. The study concludes that PLA-pectin composites represent a promising solution for addressing environmental concerns related to plastic waste, aligning with sustainable development goals. Future research should focus on optimizing formulation and expanding the range of biopolymers used in composite development.

KEYWORDS: PLA, Bioplastics, Hydrophilicity, Environmental sustainability, Pectin.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to climate awareness among people the demand of environment friendly products is increased. In which use of polythene as carrying bags, packaging, lamination etc. are quite difficult to eliminate because of its high strength and durability. The consumption of for polyethylene(PE) in India is approximately six million metric tons in the financial year 2021-2022(Shanker et al. 2023). However in 2022, the use of PE packaging increased to 52% since 1990(Muhib et al. 2023). This demand of PE is increasing significantly and expected to 5.6% per annum(H. Cheng et al. 2022). The harmful impacts of plastic production, recycling, and disposal are significant, contributing to approximately 85% of the total carbon footprint. These processes release large amounts of greenhouse gases, making plastic pollution a major environmental concern(Cabernard et al. 2022). To reduce carbon footprints, bio-based plastics are synthesized by polymerizing monomers extracted from plants, animals, and microorganisms. These plastics serve as an alternative to traditional polyethylene (PE) and, being derived from renewable biological sources, are also

biodegradable.(Rosenboom, Langer, and Traverso 2022). Polylactic acid (PLA) is a bio-based, biodegradable polyester synthesized from lactic acid monomers, which are derived from renewable sources such as corn and food waste (Momayez, Karimi, and Horváth 2019). Due to their inherent low strength, bioplastics are often reinforced with natural fibers or bio-fillers to enhance their mechanical properties while maintaining biodegradability. Various biodegradable polymers, including polylactic acid (PLA), starch, and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), are commonly used in such applications(Zhao et al. 2023). Polylactic Acid (PLA) has a density of 1.25 g/cm³, a glass transition temperature ranging from 54 to 56°C, and a melting point between 120°C to 170°C. Its molecular weight is approximately 66,000 g/mol, and it exhibits a tensile strength between 21 and 60 MPa (Cai et al. 2002; Farah, Anderson, and Langer 2016). PLA composites address brittleness and low heat resistance through reinforcement. For instance, adding wood flour (20–40 wt.%) achieves a tensile strength of 63.3 MPa and a tensile modulus of 5.3 GPa. Silk reinforcement (1–7 wt.%) results in a tensile strength of 62.08 MPa and a tensile modulus

of 2.54 GPa. The inclusion of PBAT (20 wt.%) provides a tensile strength of 66.1 MPa with a density of 1.078 g/cm³, while PHA (20 wt.%) yields a tensile strength of 25.4 MPa and a density of 1.2 g/cm³(Cheung et al. 2008; Huda et al. 2006; Injorhor et al. 2023; Spiridon, Darie, and Kangas 2016). The thermal conductivity is important term in food industry if a material like chocolates required to be packed with films with low thermal conductivity which prevents them from softening (Chen et al. 2020). However, the same low thermal conductivity can hinder effective heat dissipation, making these films unsuitable for packaging electronic items (Chaudhry, Mabrouk, and Abdala 2020; Zhao and Hu 2021). The thermal conductivity of polyethylene (PE) typically ranges from 0.25 to 0.4 W/m-K, depending on the type of PE and its crystallinity (Travaš, Rujnić Havstad, and Pilipović 2023).

The untreated polyethylene (PE) has a water contact angle of approximately 85°, indicating its hydrophobic nature. However, for applications such as adhesion to coatings, inks, or adhesives, plasma treatment makes polyethylene more hydrophilic, resulting in a decreased water contact angle (Andrew D. Gilpin and Dillingham 2015). Similarly, PLA surface is also hydrophobic in nature with contact angle of 75–85°(Tümer, Erbil, and Akdoğan 2022).An another biodegradable water-soluble polymer extracted from plant cell walls is Pectin which is particularly extracted from citrus fruits like oranges is widely used in food industry like jams and yogurts due to this gelling characteristics it is also suitable of producing thin films(Bariş et al. 2022). The pectin obtained from waste orange peels also aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals outlined in Agenda 2030 (Ghafari 2022). Pectin is extracted using acidic treatment with hydrochloric, nitric, or sulfuric acid, followed by heating. Among numerous methods “Hot-water” assisted with citric acid are more efficient and yield higher-quality pectin(Benassi, Alessandri, and Vassalini 2021).To replace PE with bioplastics, the tensile strength of the bioplastics should range between 2.69 and 70 MPa(Szlachetka et al. 2021). The bio-plastics without filler is evidence with 0.3-19 MPa of tensile strength and reinforcing with titanium nano particles increases the tensile strength to 3.5 MPa (Amin, Chowdhury, and Kowser 2019; Gabriel, Solikhah, and Rahmawati 2021; Xia et al. 2021). The Shore D hardness of PE typically falls within the range of 30-60 (Vian and Denton 2018). Reinforcement of PLA with 1-5% by weight has been shown to achieve the highest fracture strength and toughness(Material 2024; Ramirez, Agaliotis, and Pettarin 2024).

The primary objective of this study is to develop a PLA-based bioplastic reinforced with 1-3%

extracted pectin. To mitigate the risk of agglomeration and the consequent reduction in mechanical strength, the pectin content is limited to a maximum of 3%. Tensile testing, hardness testing, and water contact angle measurements are conducted in accordance with ASTM standards.

2 METHODOLOGY

Pectin was extracted from orange peel to be used as a filler material. The peel was washed with distilled water, sun-dried, and ground into fine powder. Five grams of the powder were mixed with citric acid solution at pH levels of 1.5, 2.5, and 3.5, then stirred for 45 minutes at 50°C. After cooling, the solution was filtered and treated with ethanol to precipitate the pectin. The jelly-like precipitate was washed with ethanol for purity and dried in a hot air oven at 55°C for 3 hours, yielding pectin particles approximately 2 microns in size (Figure 1)(Dey et al. 2021).

Fig.1 Fine powder of pectin extracted from orange peel for use as a filler material.

To produce a PLA film composite, 5 grams of polylactic acid (PLA) granules are dissolved in 100 mL of chloroform to achieve a 5% (weight/volume) concentration (Figure 2(A)). Pectin particles are dispersed in the PLA matrix, with the pectin dissolved in water along with cross-linking agents' calcium chloride for better compatibility with polymer matrix (Figure 2(B))(Safaei and Roosta Azad 2020).

Fig. 2 (A) Dissolving 5 grams of PLA granules in 100 mL of chloroform to achieve a 5% concentration. (B) Dispersion of pectin particles in the PLA matrix, using water and cross-linking agents' calcium chloride.

The PLA-pectin mixture is stirred continuously for 30 min at 200 rpm (Figure 3) before being poured onto a flat surface, such as a glass plate, for film casting. A casting knife is used to evenly spread the film, which is then allowed to cure at room

temperature for one day. Finally, the film is post-cured in a hot air oven at 60°C for 3 hours to enhance its mechanical properties (Safaei and Roosta Azad 2020). The PLA and pectin mixture is categorized as a composite material according to the reinforcing of pectin in PLA as shown in Table 1. The samples were prepared based on the composite designations provided in Table 1. Five specimens were designated for tensile testing (Figure 4), hardness testing, and thermal conductivity (Figure 5) measurements, following the standards of ASTM D3039(Saba, Jawaaid, and Sultan 2019), ASTM D2240(Kariper 2016), and ASTM D3850(Venkatash 2024). Water contact angle assessments were conducted using the sessile drop test (Srivastava, Sarangi, and Singh 2024).

Fig. 3 Continuous stirring of the PLA-pectin mixture for 30 minutes at 200 rpm before pouring onto a flat surface.

Table 1 Composition of PLA and pectin mixture categorized as a composite material, detailing the weight percentages of PLA matrix and pectin reinforcement.

Composite Designation	PLA matrix (wt.%)	Pectin reinforcement (wt.%)
PLA 1	100	-
PLA 2	99	1%
PLA 3	98	2%
PLA 4	97	3%

Fig.4 Tensile test specimens of composite samples PLA 1, PLA 2, PLA 3, and PLA 4(Left to right)

Fig.5: Thermal conductivity test specimens of composite samples PLA 1, PLA 2, PLA 3, and PLA 4.

3 RESULTS

The results of tensile tests conducted on five specimens from each sample, following ASTM standards, are summarized in Table 2. Table 3 presents the hardness test results for five specimens from each of the four samples, measured using a Shore-D durometer, which features a hardened steel rod with a 30° conical point and a 0.1 mm radius tip. The thermal conductivity test results, obtained using the Lee disc method in accordance with ASTM standards, are displayed in Table 4. The sessile drop method was used to measure the water contact angle on each sample. The results are recorded in Table 5 and illustrated in Figure 6.

Table 2 Tensile test results for five specimens from each sample, conducted according to ASTM D3039 standards shown as mean±SD.

Composite Designation	Tensile Strength (N/mm ²)	Elongation at Break (%)
PLA 1	3.8625±0.1108	16.125±0.225
PLA 2	4.0625±0.1108	9.9875±0.154
PLA 3	4.8±0.147	18.2±0.536
PLA 4	4.9525±0.073	19.15±0.5515

Table 3 Hardness test results for five specimens from each of the four samples, measured using a Shore-D durometer shown as mean±SD.

Composite Designation	Hardness Value
PLA 1	68.54±1.121
PLA 2	73.92±0.791
PLA 3	78.48±1.413
PLA 4	78.98±0.7085

Table 4 Thermal conductivity test results obtained using the Lee disc method in accordance with ASTM D2240 standards shown as mean±SD.

Composite Designation	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)
PLA 1	0.356±0.036
PLA 2	0.312±0.016
PLA 3	0.272±0.0192
PLA 4	0.23±0.0158

Table 5: Water contact angle and density measurements for each sample using the sessile drop method with constant Humidity ratio of 60%.

Composite Designation	Contact Angle (o)	Density(g/cc)
PLA 1	78	1.25
PLA 2	72	1.27
PLA 3	66	1.28
PLA 4	63	1.28

Fig. 6: Water contact angle measurements for each sample, shown in four separate images, illustrating the sessile drop method (PLA-1, 2,3 and 4).

Table 6: Comparison of mechanical, thermal, and surface properties of PLA-pectin composites from the present study with pectin-based edible films and PLA composites from previous studies.

Property	PLA Composites (Present Study) in MPa	Pectin-Based Edible Films	Reference
Tensile Strength (MPa)	3.86–4.95	4.00 to 7.00 (Pectin, Glycerol)	(Asfaw, Tafa, and Satheesh 2023)
		1.43 to 6.41 (Gamma-aminobutyric acid, Pectin)	(Meerasri and Sothornvit 2020)
		4.48 to 69.33 (Glycerol, Polyethylene Glycol, Pectin)	(Cabello et al. 2015)

		22.5 to 42.3 (Pectin, Alginate)	(Galus and Lenart 2013)
Elongation at Break (%)	9.99–19.15	22.21 to 29.5 (Pectin, Glycerol)	(Asfaw et al. 2023)
		8.78 to 32.15 (Gamma-aminobutyric acid, Pectin)	(Meerasri and Sothornvit 2020)
Shore Hardness D	68.54-78	77-84 (PLA)	(Zeng et al. 2022)
		68.4 -71.7 (modified PLA composites with 5% inclusion)	(Oksiuta et al. 2020)
Thermal conductivity (W/m-K)	0.23-0.356	0.183(W/m-K)	(Spinelli et al. 2022)
		0.320 W/m-K (PLA reinforced multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) and 0.6620 W/m-K (GNPs-graphene nanoplates)	(Spinelli et al. 2022)
		0.715 W/m-K (Surface treated PLA)	(Lule and Kim 2019)
Water Contact Angle(o)	63-78	109.31o(PLA membrane)	(X.-Q. Cheng et al. 2022)
		24 o(PLA/HA -70/30)	(Laput et al. 2019)
		34o(PLA/18% nano hydroxy apatite (nHA))	(Liu et al. 2015)
Density(g/cc)	1.25-1.28	1.24 g/cc (Poly(lactic acid) / Poly(ethylene glycol) blends)	(Bijarimi et al. 2016)
		1.28 g/cc (Carbon fiber-reinforced PLA composite wires)	(Wang et al. 2024)
		1.25 g/cc (PLA 305 1D pellets)	(Dong et al. 2014)

Table 2 shows that tensile strength of PLA-pectin composites increases with pectin content from 0% to

3%, with PLA 1 at 3.8625 N/mm² and PLA 4 at 4.9525 N/mm². Initial elongation decreases in PLA 2 (1% pectin) but increases in PLA 4 (19.15%), indicating improved flexibility. However, tensile strengths (3.86 to 4.95 MPa) and elongation at break (9.99% to 19.15%) are lower than polyethylene (PE). The hardness of PLA-pectin composites ranges from 68.54 to 78.98 (Table 3), making them harder than PE, which has a Shore D hardness of 30 to 60 (Vian and Denton 2018). Thermal conductivities of PLA-pectin (0.23 to 0.356 W/m-K) as shown in Table 4 are comparable to PE's 0.33 W/m-K (Travaš et al. 2023). PLA-pectin composites are more hydrophilic (contact angles of 63° to 78°) than PE (85°) [18], enhancing biodegradability as shown in Table 5. Densities of PLA-pectin composites (1.25 to 1.28 g/cc) as shown in Table 5 are higher than PE's (0.91 to 0.96 g/cc) (Han 2014), affecting weight-sensitive applications.

However, comparing with Pectin-Based Edible Films with the present study as shown in Table 6. The tensile strength of PLA-pectin composites increases with pectin content, ranging from 3.8625 N/mm² for PLA 1 (pure PLA) to 4.9525 N/mm² for PLA 4 (3% pectin), indicating effective reinforcement. However, this range (3.86–4.95 MPa) is lower than pectin-based edible films reinforced with glycerol or polyethylene glycol (4.00–69.33 MPa). Elongation at break is highest for PLA 4 (19.15%) and lowest for PLA 2 (9.99%), showing improved flexibility with pectin reinforcement; however, it remains slightly lower than other pectin-based films (8.78%–32.15%). Hardness, measured by Shore D, increases with pectin content from 68.54 for PLA 1 to 78.98 for PLA 4, indicating enhanced stiffness, though still below the hardness range of unmodified PLA (77–84). Thermal conductivity decreases with pectin, from 0.356 W/m-K in PLA 1 to 0.23 W/m-K in PLA 4, suggesting better insulation properties compared to composites like PLA with multi-walled carbon nanotubes, which can reach 0.662 W/m-K. Water contact angles decrease with pectin, from 78° for PLA 1 to 63° for PLA 4, indicating increased hydrophilicity, which is beneficial for biodegradability. Finally, the density of the composites remains consistent at 1.25 to 1.28 g/cc, showing that adding up to 3% pectin does not significantly change the bulk density, aligning with other PLA-based materials. PLA-pectin composites provide a sustainable alternative to polyethylene (PE) across various applications. PLA 1 is suitable for rigid packaging and structural components, while PLA 2 excels in flexible packaging and food wraps. PLA 3 serves well for biodegradable single-use items, like cutlery and plates, due to its high tensile strength and elongation. PLA 4, with enhanced

hydrophilicity, is ideal for agricultural films and biodegradable non-woven fabrics. Overall, these composites effectively replace PE, promoting sustainability and biodegradability.

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, PLA-pectin composites demonstrate significant potential as a sustainable alternative to polyethylene in various applications. The study shows that incorporating pectin enhances the mechanical properties, flexibility, and hydrophilicity of PLA. The tensile strength of the composites ranges from 3.86 N/mm² for PLA 1 to 4.95 N/mm² for PLA 4, indicating effective reinforcement with pectin. PLA 1 is suitable for rigid packaging and structural components, while PLA 2, with a tensile strength of 4.06 N/mm², offers flexibility for food wraps. The superior tensile strength and elongation at break of PLA 3 (4.8 N/mm² and 18.2%, respectively) make it appropriate for biodegradable single-use items like cutlery and plates. PLA 4, with the highest pectin content and an elongation at break of 19.15%, demonstrates enhanced hydrophilicity, making it ideal for agricultural films and biodegradable non-woven fabrics. Overall, these composites not only address the growing demand for eco-friendly materials but also contribute to the reduction of plastic waste, aligning with sustainable development goals. Future research could focus on optimizing pectin content and exploring additional biopolymers to further enhance the performance of PLA-based composites.

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